

responsible for the yield increase. At this stage, the response to different levels of pyrite appears to be due to widespread deficiencies of many elements in Uttar Pradesh soil. *ℒ*

Effect of nitrogen source, rate, and placement method on growth and yield

G.R. Singh and T.A. Singh, Soil Science Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, U.P. India

The efficiency of urea, urea supergranules (USG), and NPK (12-32-16) rates and placement methods in flooded lowland transplanted rice was studied in 1984 kharif. The design used three N rates and placement methods in a randomized block design with three replications.

Twenty-three-day-old Jaya rice seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing. The soil (Beni silty clay loam) had pH 7.2, 1.51% organic C, CEC 23.91 meq/ 100 g of soil, and percolation rate of 15.3 mm/d. Treatments are described in the table.

All plots except NPK treatments received 28 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 26 kg K/ha as muriate of potash.

Effect of source, rate, and placement of N on yield attributes of rice.

Treatment ^a		Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/m ²	Gram yield (t/ha)
Rate (kg N/ha)	Source and application			
0	(control)	75.3	157	2.9
60	Urea, 3 splits	78.0	199	4.1
90	Urea, 3 splits	81.9	218	5.1
120	Urea, 3 splits	84.2	239	5.4
60	USG B&I at transplanting	76.8	207	4.0
90	USG B&I at transplanting	79.6	220	4.8
120	USG B&I at transplanting	84.0	290	5.2
60	USG deep placed 11 DT	84.4	243	4.8
90	USG deep placed 11 DT	88.2	253	5.3
120	USG deep placed 11 DT	89.2	303	5.4
60	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	77.9	191	4.0
90	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	81.5	209	4.9
120	2/3 N as USG B&I at transplanting + 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation	84.4	214	5.3
120	24 kg N/ha at transplanting + 96 kg N/ha as urea in 2 equal splits at tillering & panicle initiation	90.8	296	5.8
120	24 kg N/ha at transplanting + 96 kg N/ha as USG deep placed 11 DT	89.3	308	5.1
CD (0.05)		2.6	14	0.2

^a B&I = broadcast and incorporated. Deep placed USG is put in the center of 4 hills in alternate rows at 8-10 cm depth. DT = days after transplanting.

At 60 kg N/ha, yields from deep placed USG were significantly superior to those from 3 splits of urea, USG broadcast and incorporated (B&I) at transplanting, and 2/3 N as USG B&I

at transplanting, and 1/3 N as urea at panicle initiation. Above 60 kg N/ha, response to deep placed USG was less than the response to N applied by other methods. *ℒ*

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Energy use in rice-based farming system in India

A. S. Saini, Regional Research Station, Dhaulakuan 173 001 District Sirmour (H.P.); R.K. Patel and R.V. Singh, National Dairy Research Institute (NDRI), Karnal 132 001 (Haryana), India

We estimated and compared the energy requirements of rice and wheat crops at farmers' and improved levels of technology. Data on direct energy inputs in rice and wheat were obtained from a randomly selected sample of 191 farmers

for one agricultural year. Indirect energy inputs (which represent about 20% of the total direct energy inputs) are not accounted for in this study.

The data on per hectare energy input and output for rice and wheat at farmer's field (farmers' technology) and NDRI demonstration unit (improved technology) are presented in the table. The data suggest that farmyard manure and chemical fertilizer were the major energy inputs for rice and wheat crops under both technology levels. The use of energy from these sources was comparatively higher under the

improved technology level than under the farmers' technology level for both crops. Bullock and human labor were the next important energy inputs under farmers' technology and machinery under improved technology.

Under farmers' technology, energy use was higher for wheat; under improved technology, energy use was higher for rice. Total energy inputs, in general, were higher under farmers' technology. Nevertheless, energy output was higher with the improved than with the farmers' technology, resulting in a relatively higher energy output-input